

FIRST STEPS IN THE ENDEAVOUR TO DETERMINE PARTICLE PROPERTIES IN THE DIRECT REDUCTION PROCESS OF IRON ORE PELLETS

Salvatore la Manna^a, Klidi Qyteti^b, Sina Zinatlou Ajabshir^a, Diego Barletta^a, Viktor Scherer^b, Massimo Poletto^a

^a Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Salerno, Via Giovanni Paolo II, 132, 84084 Fisciano, SA, Italy

^b Department of Energy Plant Technology, Ruhr-University Bochum, Universitätsstraße 150, 44780 Bochum, Germany

ABSTRACT

The direct reduction (DR) of iron ores provides an environmentally friendly alternative to conventional blast furnace steelmaking, resulting in significantly reduced CO₂ emissions. In a DR shaft furnace, coarse and packed iron ore particles, as pellets or lumps, descend under gravity while a reducing gas mixture of hydrogen and carbon monoxide (syngas) crosses the system in the upward direction. During this descent, the mechanical properties of the particles, such as friction and cohesion, affect the ore flow and are influenced by temperature and composition changes due to gas-solid reactions. Quantifying solid phase flowability is crucial to prevent particle interlocking and stagnant zones. Standard apparatus and procedures were developed to characterise bulk flow properties for fine powders and cannot be used with coarse iron ores. This study addresses the challenge of pioneering an approach to calibrate a discrete element method (DEM) applied to coarse particles starting from experimental data, extracted from customised experiments run on slightly modified rotational shear testing equipment in conditions that do not allow the derivation of bulk properties, to characterize a simplified mechanical system composed of coarse wooden spheres. The close agreement between experimental data and DEM simulations validates this approach for large particles. The next step is to characterise iron oxide pellets under process conditions to understand the impact of cohesion and friction on flow properties and refine DEM model parameters for simulating the DR process accurately.

KEYWORDS: rotational shear cell, coarse particles, wooden spheres, cohesion, DEM simulation

INTRODUCTION

The urgent need to reduce CO₂ emissions in energy-intensive industries underscores the critical role of sustainable practices in mitigating climate change. Industrial sectors account for approximately 31% of global emissions, with steel and cement production being major contributors. Among these, the steel industry stands out due to its reliance on the conventional blast furnace process. This method uses coke both to reduce iron oxide (producing CO) and to generate heat necessary for the endothermic reaction and to keep high the reaction kinetics. Unfortunately, this process emits approximately 1.8 tonnes of CO₂ per tonne of steel, significantly contributing to 7% to 9% of global fossil fuel emissions.

A fundamental shift in steel production processes is imperative to align with the climate targets set by the Paris Agreement. One promising avenue involves replacing coke with hydrogen as the reducing agent for iron oxide, leading to a substantial reduction in CO₂ emissions. The EU-funded project "Maximise H₂ Enrichment in Direct Reduction Shaft Furnaces" (MaxH₂DR) focuses precisely on exploring the feasibility of this green transition. In this context, the use of hydrogen-rich gas streams in direct reduction shaft furnaces is investigated. In these furnaces, pellets and lumps of materials move downwards, and changes in temperature, gas composition, and particle stress significantly impact their flow properties. Therefore, changes in the flow behaviour of pellets during the reduction process require further study under process conditions using standard instruments developed for measuring the bulk flow behaviour of granular materials.

Conventional designs, devices and theoretical approaches primarily focus on powders made of small particles (size <1 mm). However, the reduction process of iron oxides involves coarse particles (larger than 10 mm), which renders standard procedures and equipment inadequate for characterising and describing the system according to the standard continuum approach used in powder mechanics. The large particle size in this process and the conversion process progressing within the particle in its descent make using the DEM approach particularly interesting. Our research aims to establish a specialised method for characterising coarse particles, with the ultimate goal of extracting significant DEM parameters relevant to the particle flow from shear testing of iron oxide pellets under process conditions.

A monodisperse sample of 6 mm wooden spheres with a particle density of approximately 0.79 kg/m³ as test material was selected. Preliminary tests were conducted at the University of Salerno (UNISA) using a slightly modified version of the standard Schulze rotational shear tester with the aim of determining the feasibility of measuring the friction between large model wood particles and of producing data based on tests where the cohesion between the particles was simulated with the addition of a cohesive agent between the particles. The experimental data obtained from a two-step procedure involving pre-shear and shear sequences were used to calibrate the DEM model.

The shear cell device comprises a lid and a trough. During testing, the trough continuously rotates and contains the sample. The lid, equipped with vanes, compresses the sample under an applied load, creating a shear plane within the material in a given depth that is a function of the vane's height. Then, the sample is vertically compressed, and the shear stress is measured, allowing for the quantification of friction phenomena between particles. To analyse a non-standard material made of large particles of about 1 cm in size, a purposely designed lid with a new vane geometry bearing 12 rectangular section vanes, each measuring 1 mm in thickness, 12 mm in height, and 48 mm in width, replaced the original lid with 20 rectangular section vanes whose height was limited to 5 mm which was deemed to be non-adequate for 10 mm particles. The other geometric parameters of the lid remained unchanged: an annular shape with an inner diameter of 102 mm and an outer diameter of 198 mm. The trough and the lid define a sample volume with the shape of a rectangular section toroid with dimensions of 40 mm (thickness) x 100 mm (inner diameter) x 200 mm (outer diameter).

The experiments followed a nearly conventional two-step procedure, which was used to collect raw data to be confronted with DEM:

- a pre-shear step in which the maximum normal load was applied on the lid, consolidating the sample and ensuring a consolidation condition for all the shear steps; loads of 30 and 50 N were investigated.
- a shear step in which a reduced load was applied, and the torque acting on the lid was measured; data analysis involved graphically detecting the failure condition corresponding to the incipient motion of particles.

Figure 1 reports the data obtained using 6mm uncoated wooden spheres and 30 N for the pre-shearing condition. Over time, three parameters are reported: the normal load applied to the lid, the torque measured on the lid, and the displacement of the lid.

Figure 1. The normal load applied to the lid during the test (in orange), the measured torque (in green) and the measured displacement of the lid (in blue).

The set of the applied normal force applied on the lid is reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Sets of applied loads for pre-shear and shear tests in the sample.

	Set 1	Set 2
Pre-shear [N]	50	30
Shear [N]	30	20
	20	10
	10	5
	5	3
	3	1
	1	

Commercial grease was used as a cohesive agent to reproduce cohesive forces between macroscopic particles operating at atmospheric conditions. In this scenario, the wooden spheres' mass, the number of particles, and the mean shear velocity remained constant. Consequently, the solid mass was fixed at 414.4 g. To coat the volume of the corresponding 4404 wooden spheres with a 0.5 mm layer of thickness, 251 g of grease was mixed with the spheres. The same two sets of force for the pre-shearing (30 and 50N) were investigated for both coated and uncoated wooden spheres.

In Figure 2 the three conducted repetitions are represented in a unique curve and compared with the results obtained from the uncoated wooden particles; here, the highest value of the torque during the shear phase is represented as a function of the applied normal load.

Figure 2. Experimental results, reporting average torque as a function of the shear normal load: a) using 30N and b) 50N as pre-shearing normal loads.

Graphically, it can be seen that for both sample types (coated and uncoated particles), the torque data can be fitted by straight lines. Blue is the curve for the wood uncoated spheres, and yellow is the curve obtained once the grease was added to the sample. In particular, the slope depends on the friction forces between the particles, while the intercept with the vertical axis depends on the cohesion between the particles. In the sample added with grease, the slope decreases slightly, while the value of the intersection with the vertical axis changes considerably.

Collected data were confronted with the results of a DEM model used to replicate the observed experimental behaviour. Model calculations require the direct implementation or calculation of parameters such as tangential and normal spring stiffness. Rather than using direct calculations, mass-related model parameters were determined [1-2]. As a result, input variables like the restitution coefficient, the tangential ratio to normal spring stiffness, and the contact time were necessary to apply the linear spring-dashpot model. The adopted values are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2 Parameters used for the interaction between wooden pellets and the shear cell surface for the two simulations.

Parameter	Particle-particle interaction	Particle-surface interaction
Rolling friction	0.002	0.002
Sliding friction	0.3	0.6
Coefficient of restitution	0.3	0.7
Collision time	0.001	0.001
Particle density (kg/m ³)	720	720

Figure 3 Shear cell in the simulation approach: a) front view; b) upper-front view; c) top view.

Before the simulation started, the spheres representing the wood particles were placed above the opened shear cell. The number of particles was sufficient to fill the shear cell optimally without exceeding its capacity. At the start of the simulation, the spheres fell into the bottom ring of the shear cell due to gravity. This procedure resulted in a random arrangement of the spheres, mimicking the process of loading wooden spheres into a real shear cell.

Afterwards, the lid was positioned over the spheres, and the desired force was applied and maintained by adjusting the vertical position of the lid. The global normal force ($F_{N,tot}$) applied by particles on the lid was calculated based on the mechanical interactions. Specifically, it summed up all the individual forces exerted by the particles on the lid in the perpendicular direction ($F_{N,i}$):

$$F_{N,tot} = \sum_{i=1}^n F_{N,i} \quad (1)$$

When additional cohesive forces are imposed on a contact pair, additional energy (to overcome the tensile force in the opposite direction) must be expended to separate the particle contact.

In the case of coated wood particles, the model developed by Luding et al. [3] was adapted to simulate cohesive forces. In this model, the loading and unloading phases of a particle contact are described by a linear relationship between the normal force F and the virtual overlap δ using two different spring stiffnesses k_1 and k_2 , and a cohesion strength k_c (Figure 4). When two spheres are in contact, a virtual overlap occurs, and a spring is linearly loaded with stiffness 1 (k_1). As soon as the particles move away from each other, the virtual overlap decreases, and the spring is initially unloaded again with spring stiffness 1 (k_1). When the limit value δ_{limit} is undershot, the spring is instead unloaded linearly with spring stiffness 2 (k_2). When the force component becomes negative ($\delta < \delta_0$), the particles begin to adhere to each other, and the force becomes negative. If sufficient separation energy is applied, the particles move further apart, and from an overlap of δ_{min} , either the sphere detach if the pulling force $-F_{min} > -k_c \delta_{min}$ or if the spring is relaxed with $F = k_c \delta$ until there is no more overlap. In both cases, no adhesion forces act from then on, and the contact is resolved.

Figure 4 Extended Cohesion Model.

This model is especially useful for simulating soft particles with significant virtual overlap. It achieves this by introducing a limit (δ_{limit}) which restricts how closely particles can approach each other virtually. This constraint prevents the formation of cohesive forces that would otherwise make particle separation in simulations extremely difficult. The pull-off force depends on three factors: k_1 , k_2 , and k_c . Additionally, δ_{limit} affects how the stiffness changes during separation.

Figure 5 shows the comparison between simulation (in blue) and experimental data (in orange) in terms of normal forces (Figure 5a) and shear forces (Figure 5b). It appears that the close agreement between simulation and test was achieved, especially in the case of shorter times. Further investigation into these differences could offer valuable insights for refining the model.

Figure 5. Comparison between the simulation (in blue) and experiments (in orange): the normal load on the lid (a), the shear stress (b).

The simulations illustrate the capacity to replicate the fundamental behaviour observed during the Schulze test and the potentiality of this approach. Although achieving precise alignment with the UNISA tests posed difficulties, the simulations effectively captured significant aspects. Notably, the curves obtained from simulations closely approximated the overall trends observed in the experiments for specific consolidation loads. In the next steps, our efforts will refine simulation parameters and integrate the cohesion model referenced below into the code.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Kruggel-Emden, E. Simsek, S. Rickelt, S. Wirtz, V. Scherer, Review and extension of normal force models for the Discrete Element Method, Powder Technology, Volume 171, Issue 3, 2007, Pages 157-173, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2006.10.004>.
- [2] H. Kruggel-Emden, S. Wirtz, V. Scherer, A study on tangential force laws applicable to the discrete element method (DEM) for materials with viscoelastic or plastic behavior, Chemical Engineering Science, Volume 63, Issue 6, 2008, Pages 1523-1541, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2007.11.025>.
- [3] S. Luding, K. Manetsberger, J. Müllers: A discrete model for long time sintering. Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids 2005, 53:455–91.